

Building the EU Cancer and Health Genomics Platform

Programme	EU4HEALTH
Project number	101080009
Acronym	CAN.HEAL
Start Date	1 Nov 2022
Duration	24 months

Deliverable information

WP	8
Deliverable related number	D8.3
Deliverable number	D28
Deliverable name	Standardised guidelines
Deliverable Description	Standardised guidelines for molecular interpretation
Lead Beneficiary	IC
Type	R
Dissemination level	PU
Version	V1
Due Date	31 May 2024
Delivery Date	04 June 2024
Approval Date	

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Revision History			
Version	Date	Comments	Partner
V1	30/04/2024		ACC
V2	03/05/2024	Updates from IC	IC
V3	06/05/2024	Addition of last chapter	ACC
V4	08/05/2024	Incorporation of feedbacks from IC	IC, ACC
V5	21/05/2024	Incorporation of feedbacks from WP8 partners	IC, ACC, INSERM, MFH, MUW, Sciensano, UKSH
V6	27/05/2024	Updates from IC and ACC	IC, ACC

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Summary and objective of the deliverable

Personalised and precision medicine aim to tailor treatments to the unique characteristics of each patient, considering molecular, genetic, lifestyle, environmental, and psychosocial factors. While often used interchangeably, precision medicine targets disease prevention, diagnosis, and treatment for specific patient groups with shared genetic features. In contrast, personalised medicine focuses on individual patient needs. In oncology, precision medicine has revolutionised cancer care, improving outcomes by using genomic and molecular profiling to guide diagnosis, treatment, and follow-up. Despite limited evidence on overall survival impact, genomic profiling is becoming essential in clinical settings.

Advances in genomics have integrated precision medicine into routine cancer care, using molecular profiling to guide treatment and select clinical trial candidates. However, precision oncology's impact on health policies is limited, necessitating integration into public health practices to reduce inequalities across Europe. The EU4Health CAN.HEAL project supports these goals, emphasising the incorporation of genomics into health services for cancer prevention, diagnosis, and treatment.

CAN.HEAL aims to improve health outcomes by integrating genomic advances into national and regional healthcare, focusing on therapeutic efficacy and cost-effectiveness. Clinicians face challenges in selecting appropriate genomic profiling strategies and interpreting complex genetic data, highlighting the need for trained healthcare professionals.

Over the past 15 years, targeted therapies have advanced, with Molecular Tumour Boards (MTBs) optimising biomarker-directed treatments. MTBs match drugs to patients, especially when guidelines are lacking. Establishing consensus criteria for genomic profiling and molecular data management is essential to ensure equal treatment opportunities for all cancer patients.

MTBs use expertise in oncology, genomics, pathology, and bioinformatics to make therapeutic recommendations based on tumour profiling. They identify actionable genomic alterations to guide treatment. MTBs often recommend non-standard treatments after standard options are exhausted, emphasising tumour-agnostic therapy based on molecular alterations.

MTBs have become integral to precision oncology, facilitating collaborative decision-making and optimizing patient care by incorporating the latest genomic insights.

The Deliverable 8.3 aims to propose guidelines to select and rank, as per MTB expert opinion, non-standard therapeutic strategies based on medical evidence and clinical response potential for each patient.

Work performed

To develop these guidelines, a comprehensive literature review and expert consultations were conducted within European partner institutions of the CAN.HEAL consortium. We have organised the guidelines into 10 chapters covering the various MTBs aspects and challenges:

CHAPTER 1 – Introduction

CHAPTER 2 - Goals and Composition of MTBs

CHAPTER 3 – Criteria of Inclusion for Patients

CHAPTER 4 - How to Correctly Inform and Involve the Cancer Patient

CHAPTER 5 - Clinical and Molecular Data and Workflow IT Management

CHAPTER 6 - Types of NGS Assays to Be Used on Neoplastic Tissue or Circulating Free DNA (cfDNA)

CHAPTER 7 - Molecular Tumour Board Reporting

CHAPTER 8 - Access to Medicines

CHAPTER 9 – Training

CHAPTER 10 – Monitoring of the MTB function

The guidelines and detailed chapters are attached in **Annex I**. These guidelines mainly apply to real-world MTBs, particularly for patients lacking approved treatment options who might benefit from non-standard therapies.

In this document, we acknowledge the unique mission of MTBs and their adaptation to different local circumstances and medical needs. MTBs dealing with solid tumours, haematology-oncology, or paediatrics may have different workflows. Balancing a flexible clinical approach with the need for structured, exchangeable data is a key issue addressed in these guidelines.

In our opinion MTB guidelines should define minimal essential requirements suitable for all MTBs, keeping in mind their diversity. The CAN.HEAL consortium recognises that MTBs may adopt alternative criteria appropriate for their specific diseases and patients.

Perspectives

In a rapidly changing environment, MTBs must adapt by adopting new technical solutions and accessing updated decision support tools. The introduction of artificial intelligence and machine learning tools is anticipated in the coming years. A consensus is needed beyond CAN.HEAL to establish a European MTB database/registry, which would improve harmonisation and expand

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therapeutic options. Despite ongoing efforts, access to treatment remains a major challenge for MTBs due to limited clinical trial accessibility. Merging existing platforms, such as the Molecular Tumour Board Portal of Cancer Core Europe, is crucial. The primary mission of MTBs should focus on enhancing therapeutic recommendations, with measures proposed to improve monitoring and accelerate drug approvals. These efforts will benefit certified molecular pathology laboratories and improve patient access to clinical trials.

The data accumulated within the CAN.HEAL consortium will be key for future initiatives, clinical trials and research exploitation.

ANNEX I - MTB GUIDELINES OF THE CAN.HEAL CONSORTIUM

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ANNEX 1

Molecular Tumour Board Guidelines

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Chapter 1 - Introduction

Personalised medicine and precision medicine aim to tailor medical treatments and interventions to the specific and unique characteristics of each individual patient, taking into account molecular and genetic factors as well as lifestyle, environment and psychosocial factors that may influence individual health and response to treatment. The two terms are essentially considered synonyms and used rather interchangeably. However, while precision medicine implies establishing targeted and effective approaches to disease prevention, diagnosis and treatment for specific groups of patients who share genetic and/or molecular features, personalised medicine refers to prevention and treatment approaches uniquely tailored to each individual patient with their own set of circumstances, preferences and needs. In oncology, the concept of precision medicine has revolutionized the clinical management of cancer patients, enabling precise approaches to diagnosis, treatment and follow-up, based on a growing understanding of the underlying genetic and biological features of individual cancers. This has ultimately led to improving outcomes and quality of life. Although conclusive scientific evidence is not yet available to support the real impact of precision medicine on overall survival, genomic and molecular profiling of malignancies is becoming increasingly popular and yields clinically relevant information that can inform tailored treatment strategies. This paradigm shift in cancer therapy has largely been promoted through the approval by the Food and Drug Administration (FDA) of genomic profiling tests and their widespread use as “companion diagnostics” [1]. Since MediCare/MedicAid USA made this type of test reimbursable [2], genomic profiling has become widely available to all patients with advanced solid tumours. In line with these changes, in 2020 the European Society of Medical Oncology (ESMO) reported on the use of genetic profiling of metastatic tumours by Next Generation Sequencing (NGS), recommending its application in routine diagnostics, even though initially restricted to a defined subset of four solid malignancies, *i.e.* lung adenocarcinoma, prostate carcinoma, ovarian carcinoma and cholangiocarcinoma [3]. Altogether, clinical genomic profiling has required a radical change in the technological and methodological approaches applied to the treatment of individual patients, as well as new decision-making algorithms and new clinical application approaches.

Companion diagnostics has become increasingly important in oncology. This has led to the implementation of the so-called “targeted therapies”, *e.g.* therapies based on the development of tests allowing the identification of specific biomarkers or genetic changes that predict response to a specific therapy in individual cancers. The enormous advances in genomics occurred over the last decade have enabled the integration of precision medicine into routine clinical care for cancer patients (precision oncology). Tumour molecular profiling, including genomic sequencing and other molecular tests, is now routinely used to guide treatment decisions, select targeted therapies, and identify patients eligible for clinical trials. Nevertheless, to date the impact of precision oncology on health policies remains limited. It is therefore urgent to integrate the scientific and technological advances in the current public health practices and to ensure that the necessary steps are taken to eradicate inequalities across European countries. The EU4Health CAN.HEAL project (www.canheal.eu) embraces these principles. In building the European Union

(EU) cancer and public health genomics platform, the consortium has devoted considerable effort to innovative genomic profiling and to new implementation scenarios, including Molecular Tumour Boards (MTBs).

One of the major objectives of CAN.HEAL is to explore how genomics may be incorporated into national and regional health services in the areas of cancer prevention, diagnosis and treatment, with an emphasis on evidence-based therapeutic efficacy and cost effectiveness, as supported by a careful analysis of sustainability for healthcare systems. The ultimate goal of CAN.HEAL is health improvement for both the individual and the general population. Since inception of the “big-data” era, clinicians have been increasingly confronted with complex genetic information, which implies at least two hurdles: (a) selecting the most appropriate genomic profiling strategy among the available multi-gene testing platforms may not be straightforward; (b) decoding the information of comprehensive genomic profiling requires a special blend of molecular and clinical abilities. It is expected that the exponential surge of molecular profiling of tumour samples and consequent broadening of genomic datasets will make data interpretation increasingly complex. As a result, the gap between genomic data availability and clinical practice is likely to expand in the absence of *ad-hoc* policies to regulate and promote clinical implementation of the enhanced knowledge of tumour molecular characteristics. In this scenario, investing on creating and maintaining a properly trained, proficient healthcare workforce will be of paramount importance, too, and prerequisite to moving genomics medicine forward [4].

Over the last 15 years, significant advancements have occurred in developmental therapeutics, particularly in the application of targeted therapies tailored to specific oncogenic molecular abnormalities across various cancer types. Molecular Tumour Boards (MTBs) have been established in this context and play an increasingly vital role in optimising the allocation of biomarker-directed therapies and advancing precision oncology. Their goal is to match drug and patients, bridging the above-mentioned gap and sharing observations and experience, particularly in areas where literature evidence is limited and/or no guidelines are available. Such an approach is becoming increasingly popular not only among professionals who, on a daily basis, are involved in the management of cancer patients, but also among people responsible for the organisation of national and regional health services. It is therefore mandatory to define consensus criteria for genomic profiling as well as for the interpretation and management of molecular data, in order to guarantee that all cancer patients have equal, optimal, and homogeneous treatment opportunities based on the most up-to-date scientific understanding of cancer.

MTBs were initially established with the aim of leveraging expertise in oncology, genomics, pathology and bioinformatics to interpret complex genomic data and translate them into actionable therapeutic recommendations for individual patients. Thus, they are multidisciplinary panels offering targeted therapies to cancer patients based on genomic tumour profiling, and mostly based on tumour-agnostic (*i.e.* histology-independent) criteria. Molecular alterations of various kinds (*e.g.* genomic, epigenomic, transcriptomic, proteomic, metabolomic, *etc.*) detected either in tissues or in biological fluids (the so-called liquid biopsies) may help to predict cancer vulnerability or pharmacological resistance to molecular targeted therapies or immunotherapies. Despite the variety of available analytes and “omic” readouts, NGS is the pivotal technology to identify genomic alterations with the strongest clinical impact. Single-nucleotide variants (SNVs), insertion and deletions (INDELs), gene amplifications and rearrangements conferring cancer

vulnerability or pharmacological resistance are collectively referred to as “actionable”, a term that defines their potential clinical utility to either assign or discontinue a targeted drug.

For most of the actionable alterations that are of immediate interest in the context of the MTB setting specific drugs exist which have been already approved in at least one clinical indication, but are in clinical development (albeit not yet approved) for different tumours/indications. Most often expanding indication involves clinical testing of additional and distinct tumour histotypes (or molecular subtypes). In this respect, MTB profiling is often referred to as “agnostic”, to highlight that the main element taken into account to recommend therapy is the specific molecular alteration regardless of tumour histology. Since this process, known as drug repositioning, poses serious clinical and ethical issues, MTB patients are offered agnostic treatments under defined circumstances. For instance, it is largely accepted that MTBs recommend non-standard treatment upon clinical progression after the last available standard line of therapy, *e.g.* when there are no alternative approved treatments for the specific neoplastic condition in the specific clinical case being considered.

In reviewing clinical cases, it is possible that MTBs might occasionally recommend approved treatments, as a result of expert re-evaluation of the available “omic” data, or more accurate and extensive “omic” testing. Although standard-of-care therapy assignment is a possibility in specific cases, recommendation of non-standard treatment should be considered the main mission and focus of MTBs.

In summary, over the past decade MTBs have proliferated worldwide becoming integral components of precision oncology programmes. They facilitate collaborative decision-making and optimize patient care by ensuring that the latest genomic insights are incorporated into treatment strategies. Hence, where present, MTBs play a role complementary to that of the so-called Disease Management Teams (DMTs) or Multidisciplinary Oncology Groups (MOGs). These exist in many Cancer Institutes/Centres, but unlike MTBs their main focus is on standard therapeutic indications.

In this document we acknowledge the peculiar mission of MTBs and the fact that these organisms have evolved under selective pressure to comply with different local circumstances and medical needs. For instance, MTBs dealing with solid tumours, or operating in haemato-oncological or paediatric areas, might elaborate significantly different workflows to fulfil their different missions. As to reporting, a structured report is mandatory, although it is unrealistic to expect that a single rigid format will have to be adopted by all MTBs. The delicate, ideal blend between a flexible clinical approach and the need to generate a structured, exchangeable information dataset is one of the main pending issues, and will be addressed in the dedicated sections of these guidelines.

Therefore, diversity is highly desirable and, in our opinion, MTB guidelines should define minimal essential operational and quality requirements that may suit all MTBs. Accordingly, the CAN.HEAL consortium recognizes that individual MTBs may decide not to comply with some guidelines, as long as alternative criteria are adopted, which are deemed appropriate for the range of diseases and patients seen by the specific MTB.

In keeping with this notion, two recent publications reviewed the features of MTBs worldwide. In the first study, MTBs were classified into two distinct types: (a) institutional or (b) associated with clinical trials or studies [5]. In the second study, partially funded by CAN.HEAL, the authors classified MTBs into two “evolutionary clades”: (a) real-world MTBs and (b) steering MTBs. The

former operate in the context of Institutions and/or institutional networks, whereas the latter are appointed as central decision hubs in precision oncology trials [6]. Although the analogies between the two classifications are evident, the definition of “real-world” MTB is slightly more inclusive than that of “institutional” MTB, in that a real-world MTB may operate not only in a specific institution, but also in the context of a national and/or regional collaborative MTB effort. Classification of “real-world” and “steering” MTBs in [6] was based on the number of performed tasks among seven common tasks that can be carried out by an MTB. The study showed that pure “real-world” and “steering” paradigms are rare, and most MTBs are characterised by a mixed operational mode.

In summary, the present guidelines do apply mainly to MTBs recruiting patients in a real-world setting, particularly patients who lack approved treatment options and are expected to potentially benefit from non-standard therapies. Herein, we propose guidelines to select and rank, as *per* MTB expert opinion, non-standard therapeutic strategies, taking into account the strength of medical evidence and the chances of clinical response for each specific patient.

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Chapter 2 - Goals and Composition of MTBs

2.1 Goals of MTBs

The objectives of the MTB are the analysis and discussion of clinical cases beyond the current standard of diagnostic, prognostic, and predictive assessments. Whereas a defined legal framework for MTB function remains to be developed, the main goal of the MTB is to provide a collegial multidisciplinary assessment of clinical evidence and molecular profiling to inform the most appropriate treatment choice including enrolment in innovative clinical trials. Because patients discussed by MTBs have often received multiple previous lines of therapy, MTBs should devote special attention to the patient's psycho-physical status. It is also important to underline that the final therapeutic decision remains with the healthcare professional(s) in charge (*e.g.* medical oncologist or equivalent healthcare personnel), who has(ve) an in-depth knowledge of the specific clinical case. Hence, MTBs discuss the patients' clinical features and genetic/molecular workup results, evaluate therapeutic options (including levels of evidence, priorities, and off-label applications), and assist with treatment choices. However, by no means an MTB recommendation should be considered binding or mandatory. Since the physician(s) in charge bear clinical and legal responsibilities, it is strongly recommended that they present the case during MTB meetings and critically evaluate MTB recommendations and outputs prior to making a final therapeutic decision, which is, then, proposed to the patient. The post-MTB evaluation is essential to determine whether the recommendation is still applicable (patients discussed at MTBs may experience a rapid decline of their overall clinical conditions) and does not conflict with the patient's status at the time of actual treatment. By fostering the interaction between clinicians and professionals with different expertise, MTBs provide a unique opportunity for continuing education and contribute to building awareness, at the local and international levels, of the advantages and limitations of molecular profiling techniques and their possible clinical applications.

2.2 Composition of MTBs

MTBs require different experts able to review the results of patients' molecular profiles, discuss treatment options, and formulate personalised treatment plans based on the underlying, and actionable, genetic alterations driving their cancer. Thus, the following professionals should be prioritised for inclusion in any MTB multidisciplinary team:

- Medical oncologist (one or more) - usually the physician(s) in charge
- Haematologist
- Traditional pathologist
- Molecular pathologist
- Geneticist
- Surgeon
- Radiologist
- Radiotherapist

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- Molecular biologist experienced in molecular profiling (wet lab), reporting, and actionability scales
- Bioinformatician with expertise in diagnostic pipelines and decision support tools
- Hospital pharmacist
- Data manager/study coordinator (as applicable)
- Secretary

The involvement of a patient advocate would also be highly recommended. Depending on the case under discussion, additional expertise may be required, provided by nuclear medicine physicians, bioethicists, pharmacologists, hospital and healthcare financial experts. Patient representatives may also be invited to participate and discuss general topics and/or specific cases. It is advisable that the physician who refers the patient case to be evaluated participates in the MTB meetings, signs the MTB report (see below), and leads case discussions. Alongside the physician in charge, the MTB should identify at least another professional to coordinate, keep track and bear responsibility for molecular profiling. *Ad-hoc* programmes should be offered to address the educational and training needs of the various professionals participating in MTBs.

Chapter 3 – Criteria of Inclusion for Patients

In the light of the preambles set in the introductory section, MTBs generally will not be involved in the assignment of molecular targeted therapies or immunotherapies approved as first-line indications. This task, including state of the art molecular and genetic workup, should be accomplished at the level of Disease Management Teams (DMTs). Referral of patients to MTBs should be done by DMTs upon progression on prior treatment. Therefore, in order to offer treatment options outside indication to those patients who may actually benefit from them, a careful selection of patients to be discussed in MTBs is necessary.

General eligibility criteria for discussion in the MTB are:

- Progression after therapy specific for each histology;
- Cancers of Unknown Origin (CUP), where an upfront deep molecular characterisation in combination with standard diagnostics can increase the identification of the primary origin of the tumour;
- Advanced/relapsed or metastatic cancers, where an early molecular assessment (before or during first-line treatment) is advised to define in advance the best second-line option [1];
- Clinical and preclinical evidence of the possible clinical/therapeutic relevance of non-routinely evaluated targets;
- Rare diseases or particular histology at diagnosis with limited therapeutic options;
- Presence of incidental biomolecular data in previous analyses with identification of molecular targets for which there is evidence of treatment;
- Unusual clinical history on the basis of which it is believed that performing an extended molecular profile may have therapeutic implications;
- Young adults, generally defined as diagnosed before age 40 [2];
- Performance status ECOG ≤ 2
- Signed informed consent for the collection, storage, use of biological material and associated data for the purpose of carrying out biomolecular research investigations of potential therapeutic interest;

The individual clinical cases to be discussed by the MTB may fall into one of the following categories:

1. Cancer patients with an unusual clinical history and for whom molecular profiling is considered to have therapeutic implications;
2. Oncological patients for whom a molecular characterisation is considered to contribute to a differential pathological diagnosis;

3. Cancer patients who have already undergone molecular profiling for whatever reason, with the identification of alterations of unknown significance or alterations not involving an obvious therapeutic option;
4. Cancer patients who share specific characteristics or molecular signatures, for whom unconventional therapeutic approaches or *ad-hoc* designed non-profit clinical trials could be proposed.

The general criteria listed above should be contextualized within the specific histology for which there may already exist molecular and treatment data not yet approved by regulatory bodies, but nevertheless capable of guiding the subsequent decisions of the MTB. However, the molecular investigation should not be limited to these markers alone, but should also take into account possible unexpected alterations, more peculiar to histology other than the one being evaluated, which, if present, could open up new therapeutic avenues following the MTB's evaluation.

With regard to the timing with which these investigations should be requested, it may vary depending on the pathology in question. For certain histology, in fact, NGS procedures may be advisable *ab initio* and therefore for them the MTB assessment may already be oriented towards specific targets. In all other cases, it will be the referring oncologist who, on the basis of the patient's history, may request an MTB evaluation even during a line of treatment, after which there may be limited therapeutic options.

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Chapter 4 - How to Correctly Inform and Involve the Cancer Patient

In this chapter we provide guidelines about the information material and informed consent that should be used to obtain permission to request biological samples and data for molecular tests, and to discuss their results within the MTB.

The chapter is divided into two sections: 1. Outline of the information sheet and of the informed consent form for the collection, storage, and use of the biological sample(s) and related data for the purposes of performing biomolecular investigations; 2. Outline of the information sheet and related informed consent for the processing of personal and genetic data.

PLEASE NOTE: These documents are to be considered as guidelines only and should be adapted by each institution according to national and local regulations.

4.1 Information Sheet for the Collection, Storage and Use of Biological Material and Associated Data for Performing Biomolecular Investigations

4.1.1 Purpose

Cancer cells are characterised by the presence of different molecular abnormalities that can be used to identify the drugs that are more likely to be effective in a specific patient.

A multidisciplinary team, named Molecular Tumour Board (MTB), in charge of evaluating the complex molecular investigations to be performed in biological material is active at our institution. The interpretation of data from molecular analyses performed on a patient's tumour may allow targeted therapies to be proposed on the basis of the best scientific knowledge currently available. Expertise in oncology, haematology, genetics, molecular biology, pathology, pharmacology, and bioinformatics, as well as other specific professions, when appropriate, are integrated in the MTB.

Based on your clinical situation, at the request of the treating oncologist, your case could be discussed within the MTB in order to assess the possibility of using your biological material to implement molecular investigations on tumour tissue or on DNA circulating in the blood, which would be useful in proposing to you (patient/caregiver) a targeted biological therapy for the specific tumour. These tests can identify alterations that allow use of a specific treatment, which may not be standard for your tumour type but has been shown to be effective in other tumour types that have the same molecular characteristics.

The results are then discussed within the MTB. The finding of potentially “actionable” mutations may prompt consideration of treatments that are currently not used in clinical practice for your specific disease but that are indicated for other tumours. The MTB can also suggest your inclusion in clinical trials underway at our or other institutions. However, it cannot be guaranteed that such “personalised” treatment is effective. Finally, it is also possible that the tests performed do not

reveal any actionable finding. Regardless of the outcome, the MTB will deliver a report to the referring oncologist.

By no means an MTB recommendation should be considered binding or mandatory. The physician(s) in charge will critically evaluate MTB recommendations and outputs prior to making a final therapeutic decision, which must not conflict with the patient's status at the time of actual treatment and might not necessarily correspond to the MTB recommendation.

4.1.2 Collection and Processing of Data and Samples

The increase in knowledge resulting from the possibility of cross-referencing the characteristics of the patient and those of his or her disease, from the more general to the more specific, which now include not only clinical data but also genomic and molecular data, personal/demographic data and any other data as they are functional for the purpose, will make it possible to design individual pathways, moving away from the logic of a "protocol for all". The Institution requests your (patient/representative) authorisation to use your biological samples and data to perform the above-mentioned molecular investigations.

If the samples have been previously archived (in the Pathology Department and/or Biobank of the Institution), we inform you that these analyses may lead to the exhaustion of the stored biological material. Alternatively, if biological specimens are not available or if they are not suitable for molecular investigations, we request your authorisation for the collection and storage (at the Institute's Pathology Department and/or Biobank) of a new tumour specimen obtained by means of a solid or liquid biopsy. The solid biopsy involves obtaining a new specimen of the tumour that will be analysed by a pathologist for diagnostic confirmation. Liquid biopsy uses blood obtained by venipuncture as a surrogate for tumour tissue; molecular analyses can then be performed using circulating DNA or, less commonly, circulating tumour cells or circulating RNA.

4.1.3 Sample Collection and Handling

All biological samples to be used for the molecular investigations will be pseudonymised and coded by assigning an alphanumeric identification code, which will be the only identifying information. Only you, the doctors and other authorised persons will be able to identify the samples according to the code. The coded samples will be sent to the genomics laboratory of this Institute (or to other highly specialised laboratories), where they will be processed and analysed. The investigations that will be undertaken include analyses of nucleic acids (DNA or RNA: genomic analyses) and/or of proteins (proteomics, metabolomics).

All bioinformatic and clinical data will be managed and stored in a dedicated information technology (IT) structure, in a coded database (*i.e.* the data will not be associated with the patient's identity but only with his/her identification code) to which only authorised individuals and data entry clerks will have access.

4.1.4 Incidental Findings

Such investigations usually involve the study of many genes simultaneously. This can lead to the detection of genetic variants associated with inherited conditions, including predisposition to developing tumours, but also other diseases. This information may also concern your family members, since the genetic heritage is partially shared between blood relatives. In the presence of mutations associated with cancer risk, you, and possibly your family members, may be advised to intensify screening programmes and/or other preventive actions. If you wish to be informed on these “incidental” findings, you will be referred to the genetic counselling, where you will receive detailed explanations on the implications of the findings and on the available preventative/medical options. Anyway, these secondary results will be communicated, with your consent, only if they imply a benefit to your health in terms of prevention, diagnosis, therapy or awareness of reproductive choices. Moreover, since DNA is not characteristic of the individual person, the findings may be of relevance for the family (blood relatives)

4.1.5 Future Use of Samples for Clinical or Research Purposes

Future technological developments and the evolution of knowledge in the scientific field over the next few years may suggest to undertake further investigations in your samples for purposes that cannot yet be defined based on the current state of knowledge. In the event of a subsequent analysis (*e.g.* repetition of an investigation already carried out and not conclusive, or for further therapeutic decisions) and/or for future research, your biological material could be stored in a biobank and reused. You will be asked to agree or disagree with storage and use for further clinical and/or research test.

Finally, since Institution may be linked to other national or international centres of excellence, and that it actively collaborates with these, the biological material analysed and the data obtained from it may be sent and/or communicated pseudonymously to other research centres, university institutes, hospitals or companies dealing with medical research in the specific field of research for which you (patient/representative) have given your consent. We would like to reiterate that the data are never directly identifiable (they are not linked to first name and surname) and are identified by means of a code that can only be reconverted by the data controller and the persons specifically delegated by him/her.

The information acquired from the studies carried out with your biological material and the data associated with it may:

- Be shared pseudonymously with other researchers for the purposes of medical and scientific research;
- Be used, in an anonymous and aggregated form, in scientific publications;
- May contribute to the development of drugs, therapies and diagnostic tools.

Any financial gains derived from the development of such products will not involve direct remuneration for those who make their biological material or data available.

Any information that will emerge from these investigations is strictly confidential and subject to the law on privacy (in accordance with the provisions of EU Regulation 2016/679). Consultation of

data concerning the patient will only be possible for staff who are involved in the patient's care pathway, and the patient's name will never appear in any document or publication. The data and samples collected during the study will be stored and analysed for XXX years (*to be adapted according to national/local regulations*), which may be extended if necessary.

You are free to withdraw at any time along the way or request the destruction of any samples stored at our Institute without any need to provide an explanation. Should you decide to withdraw your consent, you may choose to have your sample and related data destroyed or to have it irreversibly anonymised, which will in fact make it impossible to link your sample with your identity.

The procedure tests proposed to you complies with the Standards of Good Clinical Practice, national and international law and regulations on Clinical Research, and is in accordance with the World Medical Association's Declaration of Helsinki for the Protection of Patients' Rights.

You can exercise the rights mentioned in the articles 15 et seq. of the GDPR: - Access, Rectification – Oblivion - Limitation of processing - Data portability - Object at any time to the processing for sending commercial communications - Propose a complaint to the Guarantor in case of violation of data processing - Propose judicial appeal in case of unlawful data processing.

This information sheet has been approved by the Health Management/Ethics Committee of the Institute. For any information regarding the use of your biological data and the research for which your biological samples are used, please contact:

Dr _____ Role _____

Contact details (email and telephone) _____

4.1.6 Informed Consent Form for the Collection, Storage, Use of Biological Material and Associated Data for Performing Biomolecular Investigations

PHYSICIAN'S DECLARATION

I declare that I have fully and comprehensibly explained to the patient/representative the purposes of performing biomolecular investigations on biological material.

I believe that the information provided was sufficient, including risks and benefits, to enable the patient to make an informed decision.

Date _____

Physician's signature _____

Physician's name and title _____

DECLARATION BY THE PATIENT/REPRESENTATIVE

CONCERNED PARTY (patient)

I, the undersigned _____

born in _____ on _____

resident in _____ (full address)

Telephone _____

E-mail _____ @ _____

PARENTS (for a minor patient)

For the minor patient _____ (minor's name and surname)

The undersigned parents:

1) _____

Born in _____ on _____

Resident in _____ (full address)

Telephone _____

E-mail _____ @ _____

2) _____

Born in _____ on _____ (full address)

| Deliverable D8.3 – MTB Standardised guidelines

Resident in _____

Telephone _____

E-mail _____@_____

CURATOR / GUARDIAN / SUPPORT ADMINISTRATOR / LEGAL REPRESENTATIVE

(in the event of the patient's incapacity: total and/or partial, permanent and/or temporary)

For the patient _____ (*patient's name and surname*)

I, the undersigned _____

in the capacity of _____

Born in _____ on _____

Resident in _____ (*full address*)

Telephone _____

E-mail _____ @ _____

(attach copy of identification document and appointment document)

The patient/legal representative declares:

- That I have read and understood the information on the purpose of the collection, storage and possible future use of biological samples and related data for the purpose of carrying out biomolecular investigations of potential therapeutic interest within the Molecular Tumour Board.
- That I have been able to discuss these explanations, ask all the necessary questions and have received satisfactory answers.
- That I am aware that should the biomolecular investigation reveal an opportunity for treatment, its efficacy is not guaranteed.
- That I am also aware that such investigations could identify the presence of genetic alterations that cause an inherited predisposition to cancer and that this may involve also my blood relatives.
- That I have been informed, moreover, of the right to have free access to the to the data obtained from the biomolecular investigations.
- That I have received sufficient information about the objectives, method, risks and benefits of what is proposed to freely decide that I want to proceed with the proposed course of action.
- That I have been informed that this consent is valid pursuant to and in accordance with EU Regulation 2016/679.

The patient/legal representative

DECLARES:

YES

To authorise the collection of blood/biopsy, storage and use biological samples for molecular diagnostic purposes

NO

Date _____ Signature _____

YES

To authorise the re-use of biological samples for the purposes of research described above

NO

Date _____ Signature _____

YES

To authorise that results of the biomolecular investigation relating to the specific pathology under investigation will be communicated to
- myself

NO

YES NO
- to a family member/fiduciary*
YES - NO
- to my general practitioner or family doctor° -
YES - NO

Date _____ Signature _____

YES

To authorise that any incidental findings related to inherited disorders that can be beneficial to me and/or my blood relatives will be communicated to

NO

- myself
YES NO
- to a family member/fiduciary*
YES - NO
- to my general practitioner or family doctor° -
YES - NO

Date _____ Signature _____

–

* Name, surname, contact details of the family member/fiduciary

° Name, surname, contact details of family doctor or medical officer

YES

To consent that the results will be made available to blood relatives if they are deemed to be useful for prevention/treatment of inherited conditions and/or for reproductive planning.

NO

Date _____ Signature _____

–

YES

To authorise the use of the data and of the biological samples for further research on the same scope, depending on technological advancements

NO

Date _____ Signature _____

YES

To authorise the collection, storage and analysis of the data obtained for research purposes while maintaining all the security and privacy prerogatives of the data collected.

NO

Date _____ Signature _____

YES

To consent to the use and/or transfer of the biological material in coded form and related data, to public and private non-profit organisations and/or companies operating in the biomedical sector, for medical research purposes or for the preparation of drugs and/or diagnostic tests.

NO

Date _____ signed _____

I have been informed that the costs of storing the biological material in the Biobank/Pathology Department of the Institute, the costs of carrying out the proposed biomolecular investigations and any ensuing medical treatment are to be borne entirely by the XXX Institute.

Date _____ signed _____

Possible attachments:

a) self-certification form in case of absence of one of the child's parents;

(b) certified true copy of the original of the document appointing the guardian, curator, support administrator or legal representative;

(c) a copy of the identification document of the guardian, curator, support administrator or legal representative.

CONSENT REVOCATION

I, the undersigned _____

revoke my consent to the collection, storage and use for research purposes of my biological material and wish that

such material is rendered irreversibly anonymous and continues to be stored at the Institute's Biobank or Pathology Department XXX

this material and the data associated are completely destroyed

Date _____

Signature _____

Name and surname of the person responsible for collecting consent revocation

Signature of the person responsible for collecting consent revocation

4.2 Information Sheet on the Processing of Personal and Genetic Data

4.2.1 Confidentiality of Personal Data

The legal basis for the processing of personal data referred in the following privacy information is found in the consent expressed by the interested party pursuant to articles 6, par. 1, letter. a) and 9, par. 2, letter. a) / j) GDPR.

The processing of your personal and sensitive data is carried out by means of the operations indicated in the art. 4, par. 1, n. 2 GDPR and is indispensable for the collection, storage, and use of biological material and associated data for the purposes of carrying out biomolecular investigations with potential clinical application under the guidance of the Molecular Tumour Board: refusal to provide them will not allow participation.

We also give information that the processing of personal and genetic data provided by you will be carried out in compliance with the rights, fundamental freedoms, dignity of the Data Subject, with particular reference to confidentiality, personal identity and the right to protection of personal data. In particular, data relating to your health will be processed and, only to the extent that they are indispensable in relation to the objective of the Molecular Tumour Board's biomolecular research and potential therapeutic interest investigations that will follow, other data relating to your origin, lifestyle and sexual life, etc. In addition, the data and the related samples will only be processed by personnel authorised by the Molecular Tumour Board and access to the computer systems and premises where they are stored will be controlled by appropriate security measures. The Data Controller in fact prepares physical, technical and organizational security measures pursuant to art. 32 GDPR to prevent data loss, illicit or incorrect use and unauthorized access (Data Breach).

The sample will be identified with a code: the personal/sensitive data collected concerning you, with the exception of your name, will be recorded, processed and stored together with this code. Only the data controller and the persons specifically delegated by him will be able to link this code to your name. In accordance with the above-mentioned modalities, the data, processed by means of tools, including electronic tools, will be disseminated only in anonymous form, e.g. through scientific publications, statistical analyses and scientific conferences. You will be able to exercise the rights governed by Articles 13 et seq. of EU Regulation 2016/679 (e.g. access your personal data, supplement them, update them, rectify them, object to their processing, etc.) by contacting: XXX.

The Data Controller is the XXX Institute. The person authorised to process the data, under the authority of the data controller is the Director XXX.

You also have the right to lodge a complaint with the supervisory authority of your country of residence. You may at any time and without providing any justification interrupt your participation in the collection, storage and use of biological material and associated data for the purposes of carrying out biomolecular investigations of research and potential therapeutic interest by the Molecular Tumour Board, in which case no further data concerning you will be collected, without prejudice to the use of any data already collected to determine the results of the research. If it is

deemed appropriate, it may be useful to inform your family doctor of your participation in this collection.

The owner of the personal data, in his capacity as interested party, has the rights referred to in the art. 15 GDPR et seq., more precisely right of access, right of rectification, right of cancellation, right of limitation of processing, right of data portability, right of opposition, as well as the right to lodge a complaint with the Guarantor Authority - (art. 77 GDPR and 141 Privacy Code and subsequent amendments).

The interested party has the right to revoke the consent previously given at any time and with the ease with which he gave it, pursuant to art. 17, par.1, letter. b) GDPR, without compromising the study and/or the validity of its results.

However, this revocation does not affect the lawfulness of the processing carried out on the basis of the consent previously given and will have the sole effect of ceasing the processing of personal data for the future and interrupting participation in the study.

for XX: by sending specific communication to the XXX with registered office in XXX email XXX

or by contacting the local DPO (Data Protection Officer) directly and/or through the doctor/study reference staff at the references given below.

Identity and contact details of:

RESEARCH CENTRE

Data Controller _____

e-mail: PEC:

DPO /RPD For XXX:

e-mail: PEC:

4.2.2 Consent to the Processing of Personal and Genetic Data

I, the undersigned _____ born in _____
on _____ and resident in _____

Pursuant to EU Regulation 2016/679, having read the information notice for the processing of sensitive data, declare that I have read the above written information notice and that I have understood both the information contained therein and the supplementary information provided orally by the staff; I further declare that I have been made aware, in writing and orally, of the rights that may be exercised pursuant to Art. 15 et seq. of the European Regulation

I consent to the processing of my personal data, including genetic data, and health data, which will be carried out for the purposes, in the forms and in the ways specifically described in the above information notice.

YES

NO

Finally, I consent to the possible transfer of such data to a country outside the European Union (a country which therefore guarantees a different level of protection and processing of personal data)

YES

NO

Date _____ signed _____

(If applicable)

I, the undersigned, exercising parental responsibility

NAME _____ SURNAME _____

NAME _____ SURNAME _____

OR

the Curator/Guardian/Support Administrator/Legal Representative /

NAME _____ SURNAME _____

of patient _____ born
in _____ on _____

Pursuant to EU Regulation 2016/679, having read the information notice for the processing of sensitive data, declare that I have read the above written information notice and that I have understood both the information contained therein and the supplementary information provided orally by the staff; I further declare that I have been made aware, in writing and orally, of the rights that may be exercised pursuant to Art. 15 et seq. of the European Regulation

I consent to the processing of my child/ward of court's data, including genetic data, and health data, which will take place for the purposes, in the forms and in the manner specifically described in the above information notice.

YES

NO

Finally, I consent to the possible transfer of such data to a country outside the European Union (a country which therefore guarantees a different level of protection and processing of personal data)

YES

NO

Date _____

Father's signature _____

Date _____

Mother's signature _____

Date _____

Curator/guardian's signature _____

Possible attachments:

a) self-certification form in case of absence of one of the child's parents;

(b) certified true copy of the original of the document appointing the guardian, curator, support administrator or legal representative;

(c) a copy of the identification document of the guardian, curator, support administrator or legal representative.

Chapter 5 - Clinical and Molecular Data and Workflow IT Management

This Chapter deals with the combined amount of information that is relevant and necessary to the activities of MTBs and with the informatic tools that should be made available to MTBs to allow its components to thoroughly assess each patient's case and make a complex recommendation. As such, this chapter also deals with oncology decision support tools (DST), which are the main focus of the activities of CAN.HEAL in WP10. Therefore, we refer to the deliverables of WP10 (D10.1 and D10.2) for a more detailed discussion of this topic and recommendations for developing a unified CAN.HEAL oncDST concept.

MTBs rely on two main types of information to make treatment recommendations: clinical and molecular data. For security, privacy, and ease of sharing between hospitals and MTBs, these data need to be standardised and stored in electronic databases.

Ultimately, the patient's information, including clinical details and genomic data, needs to be brought together in a single platform for the MTB members to review. This allows them to discuss the case and create a shared report. Adding an "MTB coordinator" staff member can be helpful to manage tasks and data before, during, and after MTB meetings. Molecular data and clinical decisions can be recorded in the interoperability module for future consultation and follow-up, as well as for report generation (See Chapter 7).

5.1 Electronic Data Capture

An Electronic Data Capture (EDC) system designed for MTBs should focus on specific information needed for the meeting, rather than replacing the patient's entire medical record. It should collect relevant molecular and clinical data to guide treatment decisions that may involve using drugs or therapies for different types of cancers (tissue-agnostic approach, drug repurposing).

The EDC should gather the following macro-categories of data:

Details	Data format
Patient demographics	Tabular data (list of parameters, fixed)
Age at diagnosis	Tabular data (list of parameters, fixed)
Medical history	Tabular data (list of parameters, non-fixed)
Specific disease information	Tabular data (list of parameters, non-fixed)
Biological samples collected	Tabular data (list of parameters, binary, fixed)
Sequencing Panel Details (genes tested)	BED file and/or panel ID
Results of molecular tests, imaging studies, and immunohistochemistry analyses (in a chronological timeline)	List of files IDs and location and/or respective structured results (non-fixed, dependent on data type)

In the setting of an MTB, data collection serves a dual purpose: research and clinical recommendations. While essential for clinical decision-making, data collected for the MTB also foster advancements in scientific knowledge and continuous improvement of MTB performance, along with the development of a cancer learning system.

For research purposes, a structured database that adheres to a European Electronic Health Record Exchange Format is crucial [1]. This will allow for instance to build multicentric *in silico* patient cohorts where the impact of rare mutations on outcome can be addressed with adequate statistical power, which should be considered one of the primary purposes of the MTB. To this end, a recommended approach is to use a data model like the Minimal Dataset for Cancer as a guideline [2]. The system should allow the selection of the fields specifically relevant to MTB discussions [3]. However, clinical decision-making often involves factors beyond easily quantifiable data. These soft, patient-centred considerations, such as the caregiving framework, patient preferences, and specific comorbidities, may be laborious to structure in a hard-wired database, but can significantly impact individual treatment plans. Such vital clinical details should also be accessible to the MTB and should not be sacrificed for the sake of streamlined research.

Overall, a well-designed MTB system should effectively balance the need for structured data to drive research advancements with the flexibility to capture the nuances of individual cases, ultimately supporting both research and clinical goals.

We may therefore recommend adopting a two-tiered approach to data collection: 1) a *minimal* dataset for research purposes, modelled on EU standards, highly structured and hard-wired in the EDC form as mandatory, structured fields, and 2) a *maximal* dataset for clinical recommendations, that can include unstructured information. Clearly, the progressive structuring of all information or the adoption of Natural language Processing (NLP) to capture all unstructured and potentially useful information should be considered an area of continuous improvement.

5.2 External Databases

It is essential to give access to all up-to-date external databases and public cancer genome databases. The landscape of variant interpretation tools within the field of molecular oncology has undergone significant advancement, with the availability of various open-access platforms aimed at facilitating the annotation and classification of genomic variants. These tools, such as the American College of Medical Genetics and Genomics (ACMG) and the Association for Molecular Pathology (AMP) guidelines implemented *via* systems like InterVar, and databases like ClinVar, have greatly streamlined the process of variant interpretation by providing standardised frameworks and curated databases of variant annotations [4]. Therefore, variant annotation databases can and must be integrated into MTB platforms. In addition, since these databases are continually updated to align with the latest findings in the field, it is critical to implement them regularly.

On the other hand, the translation of variant information into actionable insights for clinical decision-making remains unresolved. Currently, platforms like OncoKB and CiVIC offer valuable resources for assessing the clinical relevance of genomic alterations and their potential

implications for targeted therapy. In the European context, actionability annotations in the European Society for Clinical Oncology (ESCAT) scale should be embedded in automated tools, which is currently not yet always the case [5].

5.3 Logistical Support

To cater to its diverse team of specialists, virtual MTBs will have to rely on specialised software to streamline decision-making.

Such software should utilize a virtual web interface, which offers the following key functionalities:

- **Controlled and granular privileges for data access**, which may need to be diversified by the type of user. This is often a legal requirement, to maintain the chain of accountability defined by privacy laws
- Depending on the secure access provided, a **personal 2-factor user authentication** with a federated and/or institute system would be advisable.
- **Scheduling activities**: This ensures efficient planning and organization for participants across different locations.
- **Visualization of clinical, pathological, and annotated molecular and genetic data in a graphical web interface.**
- **Graphical representation** of the decision process: This allows participants to visualize the discussion flow and key points in real time, fostering collaboration despite physical distance. Professional video conferencing and reporting systems, which must be recorded and stored with adequate backup and security for privacy.
- **WEB conferencing**: MTB sessions, which necessitate the participation of specialists from diverse fields, often present logistical challenges in gathering everyone in a single location. Web conferencing software with robust privacy features can bridge this gap by facilitating secure discussions and the sharing of visual materials.
- **Field-specific knowledge**: To guide the patient profile compilation, an established array of choices pertaining to the disease, tissue, and molecular alterations is imperative to facilitate comprehensive database consultation and data-sharing protocols.
- A system to **collect the MTB recommendation** in a structured format, so that MTB recommendations can populate a database that feeds back to the gene annotation, in order to preserve consistency in the recommendations.
- A **system to match patients with clinical trial inclusion/exclusion criteria**. Ideally, this should not only provide a match based on molecular alterations, but also with clinical parameters, the real-time availability of slots and geographical constraints, in order to maximize enrolment and avoid friction due to non-molecular considerations.
- A system to allow sequential MTB process management including sample logistics, automated worklists and alerting for sequential tasks.

A promising technical solution for the coming years is the growing adoption of artificial intelligence (AI) and machine learning (ML) tools to decipher the complex relationships between tumour biology, disease evolution, and therapeutic response. While caution is warranted regarding AI use for the implementation of precision oncology in clinical practice, these tools hold

immense potential for analysing and interpreting data from diverse biomarker sources like DNA sequencing, RNA sequencing, proteomics, and metabolomics. By integrating these comprehensive OMIC datasets alongside clinical data, it will be possible to significantly improve the quality of personalised treatment recommendations for cancer patients. This necessitates a thoughtful and critical approach to AI and ML adoption by MTBs. To facilitate this, it is recommended that MTB databases be structured to comply with FAIR principles and to guarantee forward compatibility with ML tools.

5.4 Minimum Requirements

The database or platform described above, capable of interconnecting all MTB actors, together with the necessary clinical data and analytical results on samples taken and any decisions, should comply with the following general rules:

- Ease of customization of content to adhere to different realities (intra- and inter-institutional);
- Easy export of data in a format compatible with downstream analysis (*e.g.* JSON, CSV, *etc.*);
- Possibility of guided data entry to facilitate subsequent report compilation;
- Possibility of external data input via file upload (*e.g.* PDF, PNG, DOC, *etc.*);
- Dynamic fields (*e.g.* calculation of the patient's age at sampling);
- Security in terms of accidental data loss (unintentional deletion, automatic backup and versioning system).
- Reference to sources (literature, databases, and guidelines) to avoid the “black box” issue.

It should be noted that tools have recently been developed that manage a part or a superset of the tasks listed above, in institutional and commercial contexts.

5.5 Workflow

The proposed workflow is mainly based on two IT tools: an EDC database and a genomic/mutational data analysis and sharing tool.

1. Admission of the patient (by direct communication from the treating physician to an oncologist belonging to the MTB). The oncologist provides the patient with informed consent.
2. The data manager/oncologist registers the patient on the platform, inputting (or automatically retrieving from the centralized hospital DB) master data and relevant clinical information.
3. The patient is assigned an anonymized identifier (ID).
4. Samples taken from the patient are recorded with a patient_sample ID and are merged with the patient's medical record together with other specific information (tissue, date, storage, *etc.*).
5. If the biobanks adopt a different database, the MTB database should be able to communicate via API (Application Programming Interface) or other technologies to retrieve the BiobankID and associate it with the patient_sample ID.

6. The pathologist refers to the patient_sample_ID or BiobankID and adds his/her assessment by adding further relevant information.
7. Any Molecular Biology laboratory included in the flow modifies laboratory-specific fields, thus keeping track of the tests performed and the results.
8. DNA and RNA libraries prepared from the patient_sample are labelled in a standard manner (e.g. patient_sample_library_ID). Unprocessed sequencing results are recorded as patient_sample_library_run ID.
9. The bioinformatician analyses the patient_sample_library_run data and generates a patient_sample_library_run_analysis.
10. All analysable mutations are uploaded and made available through a tool for visualizing, annotating and sharing genomic data by reporting the code patient_sample_run_analysis.
11. Specialised Variation Representation System to uniquely identify variants should be used to facilitate and improve sharing of genomic information [6].
12. When the patient's sample molecular data have been inserted in the database a direct link can be used to directly access the analysis and visualization tool.
13. MTB members can privately examine data, both NGS and clinical, depending on the level of privacy constraints (clinical or not).
14. The MTB meets and discusses the case, using the visualization and annotation tool or other validated resources including literature, external collaborators and necessarily oncology specialists by pathology (if different from the permanent board members).
15. Once the various pieces of evidence have been considered and pathologists and oncologists have come to an agreement, a collegial MTB report is created. This is facilitated by the structure of the database, thanks to specially prepared fields, in which all information regarding the patient, the tests and their uncertainty limit, and the positive and negative mutational status is recorded. At this stage, it is important to refer to up-to-date knowledge in terms of usable genes and available drugs. This would allow a possible re-evaluation of the case after the start of new drug trials/studies for that mutational profile.

Once the decisions are final and the report can be called complete, the oncologist can save the version of the contents of the discussion and the results (technically, one would use a versioning system that fixes the status of a file at the precise moment: any subsequent changes would be saved as a new version).

In step 10, the complete mutational results (filtered for errors and annotated) should be uploaded to a local version of molecular database (to guarantee controlled access with authentication and groups), together with the relevant metadata taken from the database and using the anonymous ID (patient_sample_run_analysis).

It would also be advisable to adhere to European standards for sharing genomic data and anonymized metadata (link with the 1+ Million genomes initiative). Many efforts have been carried out to reach full data interoperability since it would soon enable semi-automated clinical research at scale. Unfortunately, while the level of maturity for clinical metadata has been steadily increasing to many de facto standards like OMOP (and Cancer OMOP) with the OHDSI support [7], and HL7-FHIR [8], the same level of standardisation for genomic data has still to reach a higher maturity level, due to biotechnological diversity and domain-specific variability. Nonetheless,

some packages have been lately developed to enable Federated genomics search and analysis. Among these, notable examples are *Phenopackets and Beacon tools* from the Global Alliance for Genomics and Health (GA4GH) [9, 10], Genomics in FHIR [11] and OMOP Genomics [12].

As mentioned at the beginning of this chapter, the informatic tools that should be made available to MTBs to carry on their activities also include oncology decision support tools (oncDST). While a consensus definition of oncDST is still under development, these tools are rapidly evolving and hold promise of great value in aiding clinical decision-making. The aims of WP10 in CAN.HEAL are to investigate the current DST landscape and to formulate a concept for an oncDST for Europe (EU-oncDST). The CAN.HEAL consortium describes the EU-oncDST concept as a modular, transparent, interoperable and ever-growing tool envisioned as a comprehensive system composed of multiple modules, each serving distinct yet interconnected purposes to support decision-making. The concept includes patient data and bioinformatics modules, which correspond to the current electronic data capture system, as well as the clinical recommendation module, which corresponds to the external databases in the present workflow. Connected to these modules is the MTB module (corresponding to the logistical platform) that should support the MTB discussions and provide a standardised and structured final collegial MTB report. The MTB module should also be capable of interoperating with a follow-up module that is integrated with the Electronic Health Records (EHRs). Each of these aspects is designed to contribute to a comprehensive and efficient system that supports, while not replacing, clinicians in providing the best possible care to each cancer patient.

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Chapter 6 - Types of NGS Assays to Be Used on Neoplastic Tissue or Circulating Free DNA (cfDNA)

This Chapter focuses on the types of NGS assays available for the detection of clinically relevant molecular alterations either in the tumour tissue or in liquid biopsies. It does not deal with the bioinformatics pipelines to be used in the annotation and interpretation of the results, for which we refer the reader to Chapter 5.

Clinical NGS panels used in oncology undergo continuous revision and update. Targeted NGS may take advantage of commercial predefined gene panels, but not infrequently custom panels are developed by major Comprehensive Cancer Centres and academical institutions. The number of genes covered by a commercial panel may vary widely, ranging from around 16 genes to >500 genes. The lower and upper dimensional limits appear to be dictated by the number of genes that have to be covered to meet the minimum requirements of current essential levels of healthcare assistance (*i.e.* criteria for reimbursement by the healthcare system), and the need for more genomic space for expanded profiling in order to detect complex biomarkers, such as Tumour Mutational Burden (TMB), Microsatellite Instability (MSI) and Homologous Recombination Deficiency (HRD). Any number of genes in between is expected to be in line with multi-gene assays to identify somatic mutations currently approved for clinical use (or under scrutiny) by Regulatory Agencies. Without prejudice to the possibility of outsourcing certain NGS analyses from centralised NGS providers, the commercial panels to be recommended as suitable for local and immediate MTB use should, with some exceptions, run on widely available sequencing platforms, which at the time of writing appear to be Illumina (hybrid-capture approach) and ThermoFisher (amplicon-based approach). The CAN.HEAL consortium is aware of new disrupting technologies being developed by other economic operators and providers of biomedical equipment, and will strongly recommend their use in diagnostics once these meet quality and cost-effectiveness requirements, and pending IVDR compliance.

As known, there are major differences between tissue DNA (tDNA), circulating cell-free DNA (cfDNA) and cell-free total nucleic acids (cfTNA) testing. Liquid biopsy panels incorporate various error-suppression technologies, both analytical and post-analytical, and cover fewer genes and alterations, due to the known need to compromise between panel size, sensitivity, and amount of cfDNA required. Possibly, assessing gene fusions and copy number alterations remains the most challenging task, and this is technically differently addressed by various liquid biopsy panels, depending from their use of cfRNA or cfDNA as template.

The large volume of information generated by NGS presents a significant challenge. Proper analysis and interpretation demand specialised software and expertise in bioinformatics, as well as handling approaches tailored to the computer file format (*e.g.*, VCF, BAM [1]). User-friendly platforms, like cBioportal [2] or IVG [3], can be employed for data visualization and analysis. The CAN.HEAL oncDST concept, currently under development in WP10, as mentioned in Chapter 5, presents a promising future direction for MTB analysis workflows. This dedicated solution has the potential to streamline the analysis process.

Understanding the significance of genetic variations identified in MTB analysis necessitates consulting multiple external databases such as ClinVar, COSMIC, OncoKB, and CiVIC (refer to Section 5.2 for details). These resources provide valuable insights into the potential clinical implications of the observed variants. MTBP is a genomics-interpretation pipeline [4] that offers a general framework for variant classification in terms of functional and predictive relevance [5]. Clinical bioinformaticians, wielding expertise in NGS analysis, play a critical role in deciphering complex genomic data. They are instrumental in developing and maintaining user-friendly tools to facilitate efficient analysis in the context of MTB research [6].

While expertise in data analysis and interpretation is crucial, budgetary limitations are a significant factor in the adoption of a given technology by an oncology centre. Each institution should strategically invest in sequencing technologies based on its specific needs and resources. Therefore, a one-size-fits-all approach for NGS panels is not recommended. Instead, focusing on essential ("must-have") and desirable ("nice-to-have") features, as outlined in the Pre-Commercial Procurement (PCP) bid by the OncNGS consortium [7], can provide a more practical framework for decision-making.

The panels to be applied in an MTB setting should:

1. contain not only a basic list of actionable genes necessary for routine profiling, but an extended list of genes important to assign drugs being developed, or contributing prognostic and predictive information, or detecting frequent gene alterations. All these mutational hotspots are useful to monitor disease burden and response to treatment;
2. contain genes and hotspots classified by ESCAT and OncoKB criteria, at least up to level (Tier) IIIA for ESCAT and 3B for OncoKB. It is recommended to include the corresponding ESCAT and OncoKB level for the tumour type under investigation in the report next to the variants, including SNV, INDEL, CNV and fusions;
3. comply – regardless of whether commercial or custom - with the requirements of IVDR regulation (EU Regulation 2017/746), which will come into force from May 2026. Otherwise, according to current regulations and best practices, they must be validated through an appropriate and documented verification step performed within the laboratory;
4. be modular, *e.g.* should comprise a standard panel (to be used for genetic profiling of the most common solid neoplasms), as well as expanded and more specialised panels ranging in size up to subgenomic sequencing or even WES. Other NGS panels that may be needed by some MTBs are panels dedicated to rare tumours, to cancers of unknown primary (CUP), and sarcomas (RNAseq or panels focusing on sarcoma gene fusions). Information provided by some of these panels may be diagnostic and prognostic, rather than theragnostic, in nature. Nevertheless, their use may be recommended for particular diagnostic and prognostic questions not encompassed by the ESCAT or OncoKB criteria. We recommend that “special-purpose” panels are shared among MTB networks.

On the basis of these considerations, a panel testing at least alterations classified as OncoKB levels 1-3B and corresponding ESCAT criteria is recommended as a standard tool. This selection will certainly expand considerably over time as knowledge advances and new genomic vulnerabilities are recognised.

Since MTB patients are fragile, any NGS panel and sequencing technology should guarantee a turnaround time of maximum 3-4 weeks from case enrolment to MTB decision/recommendation.

In order to reduce the risk of false positives, orthogonal validation of NGS results with techniques such as real-time PCR or droplet digital PCR, whichever suitable, is recommended, if feasible within 4 weeks from enrolment, particularly in the presence of (a) rare/non-canonical alterations in the analysed tumour type; (b) low variant allele frequency (VAF); (c) starting material that is quantitatively scarce, problematic (*e.g.* prevalence of stroma), and/or of sub-optimal quality.

Case (b) is of particular relevance for liquid biopsy assays, which are generally requested by MTBs when no recent tumour tissue is available. Low VAF and borderline quality metrics are particularly impacting when (i) serial sampling is not available and therefore the NGS call cannot be verified; (ii) the biological fluid is non-conventional (*e.g.* CSF or endocavitary exudate), or contains degraded analytes (*e.g.* urine). Moreover, in the case of liquid biopsy assays, two additional challenges are represented by the interpretation of negative results and clonal haematopoiesis of indeterminate potential (CHIP). With regard to the first issue, lack of detection of driver gene mutations in plasma can depend from several factors, including the sensitivity of the assay and the amount of ctDNA released in plasma. Therefore, it is advised that future NGS panels should incorporate quantification of the tumour fraction (TF) in cfDNA, to enable correct interpretation of the results of the assay in case no mutation is detected. With regard to CHIP, although its impact on therapeutic decisions is likely limited, the possibility that some mutations in driver genes (*e.g.* TP53) detected in plasma stem from hematopoietic cells rather than the tumour could be estimated either by bioinformatic analysis or by running parallel sequencing of leucocyte DNA.

Moreover, for tissue analysis, it would be appropriate to conduct an *in-situ* test such as fluorescence in situ hybridization (FISH) and immunohistochemistry in order to verify copy number changes (gain or loss) with a value close to cut-off and in the presence of a non-targeted fusion or expression imbalance, respectively.

Pharmacoeconomic considerations are also important. In order to provide useful guidance on reimbursement, it is advisable to draw up a cost estimate for the NGS analysis selected by the MTB with the help of a management control centre.

Finally, for MTB overall performance we should consider the advantage of WES (whole-exome sequencing), WGS (whole-genome sequencing), and RNA-seq (RNA sequencing) as a powerful trio of tools for understanding and combating cancer. Each has its own strengths and plays a distinct role in advancing cancer care. Here is a synthetic summary of their combined value:

WES, WGS, and RNA-seq offer a complementary approach. WES provides a targeted and cost-effective way to identify protein-coding mutations. WGS offers the most comprehensive genetic picture, while RNA-seq sheds light on gene function and tumour microenvironment. By integrating the findings from these techniques, oncologists may gain a deeper understanding of a patient's specific cancer, leading to:

- More accurate diagnosis, allowing to differentiate between cancer types and identify subtypes with distinct clinical behaviour;
- Personalised treatment plans, enabling to tailor therapies based on a patient's unique genetic and functional landscape;

- Improved prognosis, providing insights into disease course and potential for recurrence;
- Development of new therapies, uncovering novel mutations and pathways that can be targeted by new therapies.

WES should be routinely accompanied by germline analysis performed by a clinical geneticist. This comprehensive approach is crucial, because up to 10% of germline data sets can include pathogenic variants [8], impacting genetic counselling and clinical decision-making.

It is important to note that these technologies are still evolving, and challenges like data analysis and cost-effectiveness need to be addressed. However, their potential to revolutionize cancer care is undeniable. As these techniques become more refined and integrated into clinical practice, they hold the promise of a future with more effective and personalised cancer treatments.

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Chapter 7 - Molecular Tumour Board Reporting

In the context of the decision flowchart outlined in Chapter 5, the MTB must generate additional, dedicated reports, distinct from those that are normally deemed suitable in routine clinical practice. The MTB report must contain two orders of recommendations, which we suggest be kept well separated:

- a set of diagnostic recommendations, which include a critical review of the diagnostic test(s) performed and molecular alterations identified, and a recommendation for tests that will be performed in the frame of the MTB; and
- a set of therapeutic recommendations, centred around the suitability of the patient for treatment with a therapy in the context of clinical trials, expanded access or other form of access to non-standard therapy.

The specific features of the two documents are described below.

7.1 The Molecular Report

The need to generate a structured document emerges from the changing approach of molecular biology in clinical tissue practice, particularly in the context of Pathology Departments of Oncology Institutes. Routine molecular screening within Pathology has moved from a small list of defined molecular alterations with established binary results to long and complex lists of molecular alterations profiled *via* high-throughput techniques associated with uncertain clinical recommendations. This revolution, with its strong improvement in cost-effectiveness, has posed a technological challenge for Pathology Departments, which have to manage large volumes of unstructured data for their analysis, interpretation and archiving.

The node of the interpretation of molecular alterations has been solved differently across institutes. Roughly, two patterns have emerged: in large academic centres, a collaborative effort between Pathology, Research Laboratories and Bioinformatics Units allowed the development of institute-specific analytical pipelines (*e.g.* Dana Farber Cancer Institute, Memorial Sloan Kettering Cancer Center, MD Anderson Cancer Center, DKFZ). Other institutes, often with limited bioinformatic and research resources, relied on commercial solutions, provided by the sequencing kit companies themselves, as an add-on to standard data analysis pipelines. A key undesired outcome of such heterogeneity is the possibility of differential interpretation of the same variant across institutes/platforms so that the same patient could be diagnosed with a pathogenic/actionable variant in one institute and with a benign/nonactionable variant elsewhere [1]. Recently, networks have produced guidelines in an attempt to unify the format of molecular reporting across different centres (see for example [2]).

It must be stressed that clinical data are as important as molecular data in the MTB decision-making process.

Significant efforts have been devoted by several international consortia to the identification of a “minimal dataset” for the clinical annotation of genomic data [3, 4]. However, as already discussed in Chapter 5, it is worth stressing that the dataset required to maximise research utility is not the same as the one required to maximise clinical utility. In the context of MTBs, the priority must be given to the possibility of identifying a beneficial treatment for the patient. Multiple non-trivial clinical factors intervene to condition the suitability of a patient for a precision medicine-based treatment, which include the patient’s performance status, life expectancy, comorbidities, and socio-economic factors, such as the geographical accessibility to clinical trials [5, 6]. Such information is regularly included in the decision-making process and should be registered systematically in the MTB report.

Below are the basic characteristics of a molecular report, derived from a comparison of reports in use in the clinical-institutional and commercial world.

7.1.1 Sample and Patient Information

In the upper part of the report, information on sample and patients should be given, sufficient to define the patient, the disease context, and the specific MTB query. In particular, it is essential to include information sufficient to estimate the preliminary suitability of the patient for experimental/expanded access therapy, as this is the most common query submitted to MTBs.

1. Sample information:

- date of the specimen collection;
- biopsy vs. surgery vs. else (*e.g.* aspirate, blood, fluid);
- primary histology;
- report ID of the original histological assessment;
- anatomical location;
- tumour cell content;
- type of assay performed;
- biological material (*e.g.* DNA, RNA, both, else);
- other preanalytical quality measurement, if available (*e.g.* DIN, RIN, q200, *etc.*);
- geographical residence.

2. Patient’s data:

- age at diagnosis;
- sex;
- diagnosis;
- performance status.

7.1.2 Detail of Molecular Alterations

The molecular alterations reported in the MTB report should provide sufficient detail to allow the unambiguous and platform-independent identification of each specific variant. Attention should be taken to some often-overlooked aspects: i) precise and complete nomenclature, using international standardised codes (*e.g.* HUGO, RefSeq) and multiple unambiguous notations (*e.g.* for SNVs, both nucleotide and aminoacid notation); ii) precise reference to the specific version of

each database used for annotation; iii) additional parameters of clinical utility, such as variant allele frequency (VAF).

Specific fields should include:

- gene nomenclature using international standard code (*e.g.* HUGO);
- consistent transcript nomenclature (*e.g.* RefSeq, NCBI, Ensembl);
- type of alteration, with an associated legend (*e.g.* what is meant exactly with SNV, INDEL, CNV, translocation, *etc.*);
- the specific variant, possibly in multiple notations (*e.g.* for SNVs, both nucleotide and aminoacid notation). The use of genomic coordinates, in addition to transcript coordinates, should be strongly advised as it increases the chances of unambiguous identification;
- Variant Allele Frequency (VAF);
- ploidy at the variant locus, if available;
- a table with each database version and genome build.

7.1.3 Variant Actionability

The annotation of variant actionability is possibly the most crucial aspect in the MTB report. Until recently, the number of actionable genes and alterations *per* disease was extremely low, and annotation could be done manually with little chance of error. With the increase of approved drugs in several indications, automated actionability search systems are highly desirable. Meta-knowledge bases have been proposed to unify 6 different annotation systems, including OncoKB, by the Consortium for Variant Interpretation in Cancer (VICC, <https://cancervariants.org>) [7]. The report should clearly state which scale was prioritised for the annotation, and to provide a link to the reference scale (s). It is also advisable to include multiple annotations, to highlight any discrepancy and make explicit the reason for favouring one interpretation over the other. A particular mention deserves the ESCAT scale [8]. This set of recommendations is currently widely used in MTBs across Europe as it more efficiently captures the more stringent criteria for access to innovative treatments in place across Europe. However, unlike other databases, ESCAT does not provide a granular list of variant-specific actionabilities and currently lacks an Application Programming Interface (API). This makes its implementation in automated analysis pipelines more difficult since each platform needs to develop a dedicated script to interrogate ESCAT. Nevertheless, given its importance in most MTB guidelines across Europe, the inclusion of a standardised ESCAT recommendation should be considered.

7.1.4 Clinical Trials

Linking variants to public clinical trial (CT) databases is best obtained by automated pipelines, as in some commercial NGS solutions. Some biotech companies propose Knowledge Bases curated by bots (automated) and expert panels (manual). Our recommendation is not to include CTs directly in the report, as the variant-CT association suffers from an even more rapid obsolescence than variant-actionability associations. CTs should be managed and recommended by oncologists participating in the MTB, taking advantage of up-to-date database search platforms, capable of searching the Disease/Alteration pair at different levels of granularity (*e.g.* NSCLC/BRAF MUT, NSCLC/BRAF V600E). The report generation system could be linked to this search engine (*e.g.* www.clinicaltrials.gov) to give an initial list of available CTs for the pathology/alteration, from

which the actual clinical parameters of eligibility could be considered. Alternatively, large centres may seek help from their bioinformatics facilities.

7.1.5 Information for Reproducibility of the Assay

The risk of having non-reproducible data in the Big Data era is real, which is the reason why a report should contain, at the top of the document, a minimum set of information to allow repeated testing and data analysis, such as the type of sequencing kit used (including batch number, if available) and the analytical pipeline complete with version. Software virtualisation techniques (*e.g.* Docker) are of great help in this context, as they allow the precise versions of the algorithms used to detect molecular alterations to be encapsulated in a virtual image. The same applies to annotation databases: for instance, in the case of germline variants, several consortia manage pathogenicity annotations (*e.g.* <https://brcaexchange.org/>), which are constantly updated thanks to new statistical evidence, so it is essential to report the exact version of the datasets used (*e.g.* COSMIC, dbSNP). Finally, a useful piece of information to be highlighted is the type of analysis performed: whether tumour-only or tumour-normal, especially in the context of genome-wide panels.

Further detailed information, such as the complete list of genes included in the assay performed, is a useful addendum, conceivably in the final part of the report, for additional control. The need to queue them emerges from the strong expansion of the genomic target of standard panels.

Finally, it is desirable to add information that supports the robustness of the data from a logistical and engineering point of view, such as the quality control and certification of the laboratory that generated the result.

7.1.6 Defining a Policy for the Management of Incidental Findings Related to Potential Germline Mutations

Large tumour DNA sequencing can result in the identification of potential germline mutations with important implications for the management of the patient and their family. Uncertainty in how to manage tumour-detected variants of putative germline origin can result in unnecessary and excessive referral to clinical genetics. This can cause delays, patient anxiety and unnecessary use of clinical genetics resources. Conversely, where laboratories and services fail to undertake appropriate germline-focused analysis of tumour-only sequencing, important actionable germline findings are missed. Therefore, the European Society for Medical Oncology Precision Medicine Working Group (ESMO PMWG) provided a set of recommendations on follow-up of putative germline variants detected on tumour-only sequencing, prioritising a subset of tumour-detected variants for which germline follow-up will produce the highest yield of most actionable true germline variants [9].

Although rare (<1%), the MTB predefines the possibility and management of incidental findings to the patient through the administration of an informed consent, and referral to a geneticist for advice.

Discrepancies may occur between molecular data obtained in-house and those possibly performed elsewhere. Such discrepancies may be due to biological reasons (*e.g.* tumour heterogeneity) or

analytical reasons (*e.g.*, different sensitivities between analysis platforms, PCR synthesis and reading errors, *etc.*). Such discrepancies should be reported to the laboratory and the analysis possibly repeated.

7.2 The Collegial MTB Report

The collegial MTB report summarizes the conclusions of the MTB. These are based on the available clinical information, molecular profiling and variant actionability. A collegial MTB report builds on a list of alterations to draw therapeutic recommendations. The collegial MTB report explicitly recommends and motivates potential treatments and clinical decisions. In the literature, there are few examples of the structure of a collegial MTB report. In some cases, these give rise to hybrid formats with molecular reports, containing lists of mutations with technical details that can probably be taken out of this context [10]. We recommend that the molecular report and the collegial MTB report be kept separate.

In our opinion the collegial MTB report should contain:

- A recognition header of the institutional MTB, date and MTB components taking part in the recommendation;
- Demographics of the patient for whom a consultation was requested;
- A summary of the patient's diagnostic/molecular evidence, including any diagnostic information crucial for the final decision, such as the presence of a deep or difficult-to-biopsy tumour mass;
- Summary of the annexes to the document (including the molecular report and, if available, previous NGS profiling reports);
- List of recommended treatments with underlying alteration, level of evidence and priority of recommendation
- Signature, possibly in digital form, of the person in charge of the MTB and/or other legal representatives, and the key MTB professionals providing testing and expertise for the specific clinical case;
- Attached there should be a list of the MTB members, and their expertise (*e.g.* Oncology, Radiology, Molecular Biology, *etc.*). Ideally, MTB members should be all listed on MTB letterhead.

The report should include advice as to the plausible actions needed to turn recommendations into a specific patient treatment plan. If the recommended drug cannot be provided and/or reimbursed, this should be stated.

The report should also contain the following sections:

- a) a section in which the MTB expresses its opinion on the adequacy of the analysis carried out;
- b) a section in which it declares any need for additional diagnostic investigations;
- c) a section on the possible request for genetic counselling and/or germline DNA analysis.

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Chapter 8 - Access to Medicines

An aspect of fundamental importance for guaranteeing the implementation of personalised therapies, suggested by genomic actionabilities detected by NGS assays and recommended by MTBs, is the access to medicines outside their normal indications and the coverage of their costs.

Although nowadays access to medicines outside their normal indication is governed by different national procedures and laws in the 27 EU countries, the major opportunities that can be envisaged are the following:

- 1) Whenever possible, enrolment of patients in clinical trials, at the same institution as the MTB or at a different institution, if the patient can travel;
- 2) Off-label treatment, in case the Institution is willing to pay the cost of therapy;
- 3) Compassionate use, in case the Pharmaceutical Company marketing or developing the treatment is willing to provide the drug at no cost.

Option 1) is usually preferred because it occurs within the framework of a clinical trial, with appropriate regulatory oversight, informed consent processes, and monitoring of patient safety, which ensures the highest level of quality in data collection and patient follow-up, while associated costs for drugs are typically covered by the sponsor (*i.e.* pharmaceutical companies, academic institutions, government agencies, non-profit organizations, or foundations).

Off-label use of drugs varies from country to country in Europe, but generally follows certain principles and guidelines regulated by the European Medicines Agency (EMA), as well as by national regulatory authorities, to guarantee that it is done in a safe and appropriate manner. Oncologists typically make decisions about off-label prescriptions based on the best available and emerging evidence, clinical judgment, expert consensus and patient preferences. Cost-reimbursement issues may differentially impact this opportunity in different countries.

Compassionate use programmes can provide cancer patients access to investigational or off-label drugs outside of clinical trials. In such cases, pharmaceutical companies usually provide the investigational drugs free of charge or at a reduced cost, considering compassionate use as part of their corporate social responsibility efforts, or as a way to provide access to their medicines for patients with unmet medical needs.

The CAN.HEAL consortium believes that steps need to be taken to govern these phenomena and prevent too many individual cases from being managed in total clinical and organisational autonomy. Indeed, the long-term result of such autonomy would be the accumulation of a series of cases that, although often “virtuous”, would remain framed as anecdotal, with the risk of failing to generate data that could be framed in a context characterised by scientific rigor and reproducibility.

In this regard, CAN.HEAL believes it is indispensable to establish a centralised and unified management mode throughout Europe, which uses shared rules and standards and enables the construction of solid scientific evidence. This ambitious goal cannot be materially achieved by any single institution, but rather by an alliance of institutions, through a constructive dialogue

between Drug Agencies on the one hand and Pharmaceutical Companies on the other, who should be willing to collaborate by making their products available.

A possible mode of operation that we propose as an inspiring model is the DRUP (Drug Rediscovery Protocol) protocol, recently developed by a network of cancer hospitals in the Netherlands and coordinated by the National Cancer Institute in Amsterdam [1]. For several years, a network of oncology and research institutes has been active in the Netherlands, sharing the possibility to perform whole-genome sequencing (WGS) or whole-exome sequencing (WES) on tumour samples from cancer patients. Thousands of genomes have been characterised in a centralised manner and actionable molecular alterations have been identified in >60% of the cases. This was the starting point for designing the DRUP trial, which published the results on the first 215 patients in October 2019 [2]. The aim of this protocol, which is essentially a master protocol with a high degree of flexibility in opening a theoretically unlimited number of treatment cohorts, is to be able to assign therapies to patients in an agnostic manner, *i.e.* on the basis of the molecular characteristics of individual tumours rather than their tissue of origin. The main purpose of the study is precisely to evaluate the use of targeted therapies or molecularly targeted drugs that have been approved for other indications, or are in clinical development but have not yet been approved for the specific tumour types under study. Thus, therapies are based on drugs already in use in other diseases, which are repurposed based on tumour molecular characterisation. Patients who are refractory to conventional therapies, and have exhausted standard treatment options, can access the DRUP trial. A pre-treatment tissue biopsy is a prerequisite for access, the purpose of which is to have fresh material to be used to rationalise any outcome at the end of treatment. Patients enter specific parallel cohorts (stage I) consisting of 8 subjects; each cohort is defined by drug, histologic tumour type and molecular tumour profile. If, after the analysis of 8 cases, no clinical benefit is obtained, the cohort is closed. If, on the other hand, there is at least 1 patient showing clinical benefit, the cohort is expanded to include further 16 patients (stage II). After that, if out of 24 patients at least 5 patients obtain a clinical benefit, then the cohort moves on to stage III, in which costs are reimbursed on the basis of the results obtained. Thus, up to stage II pharmaceutical companies provide the investigational drugs free of charge, while beyond stage II the insurance companies step in to cover the costs.

The DRUP protocol ultimately uses a basket study design, which allows patients with different tumour types to be enrolled based on the presence of a common molecular alteration rather than on the histologic subtype of their tumour. This approach allows targeted therapies to be studied for multiple tumour types that share similar molecular features.

At present, the DRUP protocol appears as an excellent model to be pursued in order to ensure access to rational drug repositioning and framing of patients within a clinical trial. In the DRUP protocol, patients in stage I and II receive 2 or 3 cycles of the study drug provided free of charge by the pharmaceutical company. In the Dutch model, if the drug shows benefit, the patients' insurance companies will be willing to pay for the treatment for further cycles until progression. The implementation of this approach in other countries will necessarily have to involve the possibility of setting up an enlarged table with the participation of National Regulatory Agencies and as many pharmaceutical companies as possible to cover specific molecular targeted therapies and immunotherapeutics. Currently, this is happening in other countries, such as Sweden (Magalit), Norway (Impress), Denmark (ProTarget) and Finland (Finprove), where similar programmes have been recently implemented. The DRUP approach has also inspired two EU-

funded projects, namely PCM4EU [3], a EU4Health-funded programme, and the Cancer Mission project PRIME-ROSE [4].

CAN.HEAL envisages and hopes for the possibility to expand the DRUP model to a growing number of EU Countries. In order to guarantee common rules and standards across countries, MTBs should operate with similar web platforms endorsed by Regulatory Agencies. The goal of such platforms should be to generate Real World Evidence (RWE) data, integrating the collaboration of major pharmaceutical companies and National Health systems in a therapeutic alliance for the benefit of patients. Generating RWE has become the reference methodology to explore the evolution of care and related outcomes as a function of diagnostic-therapeutic choices and existing organization, but conventional controlled clinical research undoubtedly remains the gold standard when results are used to support drug development. From this perspective, drug repositioning is not an extrapolation but a methodology for generating evidence in a controlled clinical trial.

This approach will allow the molecularly targeted therapeutic option to be offered to patients through the public health service in a timely manner, but the economic benefits will be borne by the healthcare system only in the event of success, as measured according to regulatory-accepted clinical response indicators.

Such model is not devoid of problems, which arise from: 1) the performance of tumour genomic profiling by NGS technology with different levels of sensitivity (different panels and different methods); 2) the turnaround time of genomic profiling; 3) the different test quality parameters (hence the need to establish standards for the accreditation of tests); 4) the different performance of testing centres (and hence the need to establish quality standards for the different centres); 4) the interpretation of mutational data: driver mutations, when multiple mutations are present on the same tumour (actionable, passenger, druggable); 5) tumour evolution and mutational load (biopsy site and natural history of the pathology). These issues have been discussed in previous chapters of this document.

The complexity and the different clinical, diagnostic, therapeutic, and informatics skills involved in the analysis and decision-making process will need to be addressed in collegial terms by highly experienced and competent figures. Moreover, this process, ensuring common rules and standards across countries, will have to be based on an expert system that guides the process and ensures its substantial quality. The management of the clinical case, in this highly specialised context, will have to be entrusted to panels of experts, organized in Boards pre-accredited by Regulatory Agencies on the basis of competence, verified through recognized criteria.

The DRUP protocol with a cost-sharing model and inclusion criteria shared with Regulatory Agencies will have to maintain an orientation that is in line with indispensable principles, namely:

- a) To combine the personalisation of care with caring, methodological and ethical principles that are common to different countries;
- b) To offer all patients the same opportunities, avoiding geographical or economic discrimination;
- c) To promptly adapt regulatory solutions to these new scenarios while maintaining continuity of principles;
- d) To ensure the overall sustainability of the system by driving changes;

- e) To track all patient cases in a database centrally governed by the Health Authority, which associates genomic profiling with treatments and outcomes and thus manages the context of care and research. This will enable the development and collection of reliable RWE data that can guide regulatory choices in the future.

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Chapter 9 – Training

As mentioned in Chapter 2, *ad-hoc* education and training should be offered to the various professionals who participate in MTBs. The medical oncologist usually plays a major role within the MTB, as he/she is responsible for both the identification of the cases to be discussed and the potential implementation of the suggestions and recommendations provided by the MTB. The other components of the MTB may be less familiar with the interpretation and management of molecular data. Alignment of the various professionals on the same scientific principles and knowledge base in the field of molecular medicine is crucial.

Several studies have reported that oncologists and haematologists have low confidence in their competence and skills in the biomolecular field, even if they work at international centres of excellence. Recent surveys highlighted that different specialists (*e.g.* oncologists, surgeons, radiotherapists) have different attitudes towards genomic investigation, especially when it comes to deciding when and how to prescribe panels. Uncertainty (as well as the need for consultation with other specialists or in-depth literature search) also emerged with regards to the most appropriate management of genomic data, calling for *ad-hoc* training courses and specific guidelines [1, 2].

In the context of the CAN.HEAL project, specifically in WP13 which tackles issues relevant to Education and Training, a gap analysis focused on the educational needs and challenges faced by the health professionals involved in MTBs. The preliminary results identified both basic knowledge gaps in genomics and in the interpretation and application of targeted therapies, and more advanced training needs. Management of the ethical issues and improvement of the communication skills also emerged as relevant, complementary educational needs. The lack of standardised criteria for patient selection and testing, and for decision making was also highlighted as a key challenge, along with issues related to access to clinical trials, treatment selection and awareness of the latest available innovations, all aspects that have been dealt with in various chapters of these guidelines. Organisational issues, including limited cooperation, conflicting priorities and responsibilities, and a varying level of expertise among MTB members, were also emphasised.

The identified gaps pointed to the crucial need of increased capacity building of MTB health professionals. Appropriate training pathways would be therefore advisable, and should ideally cover both basic knowledge and more advanced and targeted topics, including:

1. Genome structure;
2. Mechanisms underlying oncogenetic processes;
3. Genetic/genomic testing and interpretation of test results;
4. Elements of bioinformatics and biostatistics;
5. Latest advances and technologies in oncogenomics;
6. Databases for the therapeutic use of molecular data;
7. Communication skills when discussing genomic information;
8. Ethical considerations.

In the United States, a number of dedicated associations have fostered the development of a standardised training path [3]. Harmonised routes to ensure proper education and training of professionals involved in MTBs should be designed and implemented also in Europe.

Although in the field of oncology/haematology the knowledge of new recruits is incremental, it would be advisable to make it systematic and targeted. This could be achieved not only through focused lectures but also through properly structured training experience. For physicians who are already specialists, on the other hand, it will be necessary to develop appropriate education models to bridge knowledge gaps caused by a rapidly evolving scenario.

The concerted actions that we envision to promote education and training should ideally encompass:

- a. Inclusion of innovative, aligned topics in core curricula of medical specialist training. In view of the rapid technological advancement of diagnostic and therapeutic processes in oncology/haematology, systematic training on technical specifications and purpose of individual tests, result interpretation, and clinical application should be provided. Along with a theoretical phase, doctors in specialised training should have the opportunity to attend certified molecular laboratories and clinical centres where they can get acquainted with these topics. Interaction with relevant stakeholders (*e.g.* dialogue with European scientific societies or associations) and with competent governmental authorities would be advisable to raise awareness and reach consensus on the revision of teaching programmes.
- b. Development of advanced training courses, both in-person and online, devoted to MTB members. These advanced training courses should have a modular structure, which would make them adaptable to the specific needs of the different professionals participating in MTBs. In-person courses would prioritise hands-on training, which the gap analysis emphasised as a major need. A period of attendance in accredited laboratories could also be envisioned, as a further qualification element. Online tutorials could complement in-person training and provide more flexibility. Within CAN.HEAL WP13, the consortium is spearheading efforts to establish harmonised European recommendations for prioritising topics that should be covered in advanced training. Ideally, these pathways should be incorporated into the Continuing Medical Education (CME) framework.

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Chapter 10. Monitoring of the MTB Function

The establishment of MTBs, whether institutional, regional or national, is key to the effective implementation of precision oncology programmes based on an updated knowledge of cancer genomics and available therapies. However, it should be considered only as a first step in a scenario in which the clinical significance of mutations, the availability of targeted therapies and the results from clinical trials grow and evolve at an exceedingly fast speed.

In this regard, it is necessary to continuously monitor the activity of MTBs and to assess their effectiveness and impact over time through the implementation of a set of indicators. Some of these indicators have already been anticipated in the previous sections. Indicators may be classified as ‘internal’ and ‘external’. The former aim at monitoring the operational procedures (activity and performance) of each specific MTB, the latter are concerned with defining/monitoring the patient populations being considered and the therapeutic outcomes of MTB-recommended treatments. In both cases, but in particular for external indicators, metrics have to be adopted that enable data exchange to the widest possible extent, which implies considerable future efforts in standardising MTB reporting and data formatting/analysis. The following section provides examples of indicators, metrics and performance. It is acknowledged that in the near future considerable effort will have to be devoted to establish data sharing platforms.

In each MTB database, internal indicators and annotations should be made for each patient enabling at-glance extrapolation of:

- a) Number of patients presented/discussed per year. For each patient, drugs and number of previous therapy lines should be annotated, along with the minimal dataset described in the relevant section of this document;
- b) Number and type of tumour profiling assays carried out for each patient (particularly NGS), with explicit mention of whether they are specifically designed and validated at the institutional level, or obtained from commercial vendors but carried out in-house, or else outsourced. The type of NGS test (*e.g.* targeted, untargeted, genome-wide, *etc.*) and the panels used should be defined, coded, listed in a separated section of the database for unequivocal identification and association with each specific patient. Their implementation, *e.g.* solid tumours vs. liquid biopsies, should be highlighted;
- c) Average turnaround time for molecular profiling and data interpretation;
- d) Proportion of cases where a Molecular Report and a Collegial MTB Report have been issued (*e.g.* there should be a metric defining screen failure);
- e) Proportion of cases in which one or more actionable somatic mutations have been identified;
- f) Proportion of cases where a specific Therapeutic Recommendation based on a match between a somatic mutation and an available drug has been made. In this respect, it is recommended that not only alterations associated with vulnerabilities and resistance are listed according to their actionability scales, but that the databases are structured in a way that alterations already exploited in previous lines of therapy are purged, and the number

- of potential recommendations (*e.g.* therapeutic biomarkers not yet exploited at the time of MTB enrolment) are separately listed;
- g) Proportion of cases where actionable alterations and therapeutic recommendations (points e) and f), respectively) have been issued by the MTB;
 - h) Implementation rate of treatments recommended by the MTB;
 - i) Proportion of cases (as extrapolated from point g) where the patient has been enrolled in a clinical trial;
 - j) Other therapeutic assignments (*e.g.* compassionate use, off-label, expanded access, *etc.*).
 - k) Proportion of cases with follow-up information available following MTB recommendation, including specific information on subsequent treatments, best response and survival;
 - l) Proportion of cases with germline alterations predisposing to cancer, particularly when arising *de novo* as incidental or unexpected findings of somatic DNA testing;
 - m) Percent of patients referred for genetic counselling, separately listing referral for potential inheritance of non-neoplastic disease;
 - n) Patient-reported (self-assessed) experience as assessed by standard questionnaires;
 - o) Economic impact and sustainability.

Another important internal quality indicator to monitor is the frequency of attendance of key members of MTBs to MTB sessions, since a pre-requisite for the maintenance of high standards of activity is the collegial and interdisciplinary discussion of all cases by experts in different areas.

For MTBs that represent a network of institutions following a hub-and-spoke model, it is of importance to measure the proportion of cases presented by the hub institution *vs.* those presented by the various individual spokes, in order to assess active participation and equal access by all members of the network and patients, thus avoiding a dominant effect of the hub.

As to external indicators, aimed at providing metrics to be shared and elaborated together with other MTBs and MTB networks, we suggest that these should be included in a separate section of the database. Possibly the most important indicators, these are applicable to patients who have received a valid MTB recommendation on therapy assignment.

External indicators should be rigorously collected and stored for analysis, and may include data regarding:

- (a) adverse events;
- (b) clinical outcomes, *e.g.* tumour response according to RECIST criteria, possibly with a clear timeline at multiple re-evaluations resulting in straightforward calculation of patient-specific and population metrics such as TTP, PFS, and overall survival for each patient;
- (c) thorough documentation of biomarker and clinical data collected during MTB-recommended treatment (essential and integral to the assessment of MTB impact and clinical usefulness).

We acknowledge that there are no consensus criteria to evaluate the efficacy of MTB-recommended treatment. Randomization *vs.* a control arm (*e.g.* physician's choice) is not always possible, and may be ethically questionable in fragile patients. In the lack of randomisation, Von Hoff metrics, variable cohort approaches, and other metrics have been applied to the MTB setting. It is beyond the scope of this document to define prioritisations. However, we believe that a simple

annotation backbone as in (a)-(c) may help to retrospectively analyse large datasets contributed by different MTBs.

A special recommendation is made about endpoints (n) and (o) above. These are admittedly among the most difficult aspects of MTB workflows to be monitored. In the CAN.HEAL survey (see Deliverables 8.1 and 8.2) it was found that only 18% and 36% of MTBs monitor patient-reported outcomes and economic impact, respectively. Nevertheless, the patient viewpoint and satisfaction, particularly in a setting that is not curative, is an important goal. Its assessment should be strongly encouraged. Patients' opinions on the perceived advantage derived from MTB enrolment are crucial for dissemination activities by MTB professionals. Linked to this, collecting data and analysing them into economic and pharmacoeconomic contexts is crucial as a basis for objective evaluation of sustainability, and negotiation with funding bodies and stakeholders. Ultimately, bringing MTB opportunities to underserved patient populations depends on these two difficult-to-obtain, but highly desirable, metrics.

Needless to say, data should be kept closely secured and de-identified in order to allow future analysis of aggregated data using federated approaches. Indeed, as data accumulate and evolve over time, their storage, access and sharing in the full respect of GDPR, as outlined in previous chapters of these guidelines, will play an important role in increasing our knowledge of the relationship between a given mutational asset in a given tumour type and drug efficacy in that context. In this regard, it is essential that different MTBs work at implementing harmonised ways to store and retrieve data. Harmonised formats of reporting molecular and clinical recommendations are mandatory.

In a continuously evolving scenario where the evidence used to determine the actionability of a given molecular alteration and the availability of matched targeted therapies undergo continuous and parallel expansion, MTBs have to adapt to a changing landscape. This requires adoption of new technical solutions for the detection of actionable alterations and access to updated (and possibly innovative) decision support tools (see Chapters 6 and 7).

Among new technical solutions one can envisage in the next years the growing introduction and adoption of artificial intelligence (AI) and machine learning tools, as addressed in Chapter 5.

Regardless of the details on uniform requirements in MTB tasks, activities, and datasets, a general consensus will have to be agreed, in the future, with stakeholders well beyond the CAN.HEAL boundaries. A key recommendation by our consortium is that a common vision is mandatory towards a European MTB database/registry. This will be a major achievement and will not only facilitate harmonisation, but most importantly it will expand therapeutic opportunities for MTB patients. This common vision must explicitly take into account one major limitation of MTBs, *e.g.* access to treatment. This has long been known [1], but it is presently unresolved and still hampered by the lack of an expanded network of clinical trials/initiatives accessible to patients regardless of geographical location.

Our group is aware of many attempts to build a European vision on the subject, including the Molecular Tumour Board Portal of Cancer Core Europe, and many original publications and reviews on the topic [2-5]. Merging the different platforms is highly desirable and should be set as an absolute priority.

Overall, the MTB mission should be to continuously improve the implementation and quality of therapeutic recommendations. In this chapter, we have described measures that in our opinion will facilitate this task, by incorporating key elements into effective monitoring tools. Monitoring may not only accelerate the approval of new drugs and indications, but also enable the identification of, and access to, the most sensitive and comprehensive genomic assays. This will be of considerable benefit to certified molecular pathology laboratories. Monitoring and reducing the molecular profiling and interpretation turnaround time, organising more frequent meeting schedules, increasing access of patients to clinical trials, monitoring patients' performance status are additional, and mandatory, MTB-monitoring tasks and evaluation metrics.

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